

PROPOSAL FOR STREET MARKETS RELOCATION IN A MÉXICO CITY TOWN HALL DUE THE COVID-19 HEALTH EMERGENCY

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ABSTRACT

Due to the health emergency caused by COVID-19, the governments of each country have established important restrictions on the movement of people, products and services. These restrictions are having profound effects on the daily life of citizens by defining overcrowded sites as places of high risk of contagion. In this context, proposals that promote minimum mobility among people, as well as the distribution of food and services in a safe and orderly manner are vital to reduce the spread of the virus.

This article analyzes an alternative of redistribution of street market stands of fruits and vegetables of markets on wheels "tianguis" that guarantees the supply of these essential articles to the families of the Iztapalapa city hall during the period of confinement derived from the sanitary emergency by COVID - 19 through a coverage location model. The objective of this alternative is to locate supplies as close as possible to consumers in order to minimize crowding.

Keywords: location of facilities, logistics, COVID-19, covering problems

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the health emergency derived from COVID-19 has made us aware of the economic fragility of certain regions and localities and the problems of supplying some basic items, it has become that many distribution channels in México do not have emergency logistics and given the current situation there is no methodology or protocol that allows them to carry out their activities safely due their limited flexibility.

Mexico City (CDMX) is the entity with the highest number of registered cases of COVID-19 because it is the center of activities in the country. The health emergency has caused many activities in the capital to decrease or stop entirely due to the implementation of confinement protocols, social distancing and mobility restrictions implemented by the country's authorities at the local and federal level to safeguard health of the population. One of the activities affected due to these mobility restrictions is local trade in essential supplies such as fruits and vegetables in street markets.

It is at this point that contingency proposals in terms of logistics, economy and health become highly relevant, since the activities of the distribution channels of basic items are required to adapt to current circumstances.

The present work addresses a proposal for the location of the different market stands of the street markets through a location model with maximum coverage in order to reduce crowding and reduce the risk of infection by COVID-19.

The article is organized in the following manner. Initially, the main definitions to be addressed in the article are developed, then a brief review of the literature is presented. In the following section the antecedents of the Iztapalapa demarcation are presented, then the alternative proposal addressed in the research work is developed. Finally, the results and main conclusions of the study are presented.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Resilience

In 1973 Crawford Holling introduced the concept of resilience as a way to understand the processes and nonlinear dynamics through which ecosystems are balanced against disturbances (Calvenet, 2007). For its part, the Resilience Alliance (2020), defines resilience as the capacity of a system to absorb or recover after certain stressful events or phenomena in such a way that the system maintains its structure and functions, being able to self-organize, learn and adapt. Likewise, Wicher and Lenort (2012) define resilience as "The ability of a system to return to its original state or move to a new and more desirable state after being disturbed."

2.2. Supply chain

Supply chain resilience guide (2019), defines a supply chain as the socio-technical network that identifies, targets and satisfies demand. In addition, it mentions that no matter how vast or complex the structure of the supply chain is, they all include the same basic components, which are:

- Supply nodes: entities that manufacture, process, store and / or ship goods and services (raw material suppliers and manufacturers) are also known as vertices.
- Demand nodes: entities that buy and / or signal goods and services from supply nodes (individuals, families, companies and governments) are also known as retail destinations or vertices.
- Tiers: conventional way of grouping nodes and identifying both ascending and descending relationships within the supply chain. Tier 1

providers provide products or services to the producer or processor; Tier 2 providers provide products or services to Tier 1 providers; Tier 3 providers provide products or services to Tier 2 providers and so on within the supply chain.

- Links: are the physical and functional connections between nodes, such as communication, transport or transaction connections, also known as: edges, arches, roads, tracks, and routes.

2.3. Supply chain resilience

Currently, the concept of resilience is widely used to describe different situations in organizations, specifically in their supply chains (Cotte, 2018). In this context, organizations must be able to respond appropriately to risks and vulnerabilities to return to the desired state of operation, minimizing the variability of their activities (Murino, 2011).

Furthermore, Bukowski (2012) indicates that resilience in the supply chain is not only the ability to maintain control over variability in the face of a rupture, it also implies the ability to adapt effectively and efficiently to respond to changes within a dynamic environment. Furthermore, Bojórquez (2016) adds that the resilience process implies adequate planning to anticipate negative events in order to maintain control over the function of the chain structure, seeking to achieve a robust state of its operations.

To ensure a prompt and appropriate response by organizations within the supply chain, Murino (2011) proposes five research areas that must be integrated into decision-making analysis: supply chain management in view of resilience, robustness and security, risk analysis, vulnerabilities and uncertainties in the supply chain, prediction and analysis of market demand, life cycle cost and Modeling & Simulation. Similarly, Vargas (2015) argues that a resilient supply chain must have the following capabilities: effectiveness, efficiency, adaptability, agility, robustness, and resilience within an environment that is changing, unexpected, immeasurable, and unpredictable.

2.4. Supply chain risk management

A definition of supply chain risk says that is the potential occurrence of an incident or failure in which its outcomes result in a financial loss. However, this definition loses sight of many factors, the dimensions of which may vary with respect to time (Zsidisin & Ritchie, 2009).

A risk analysis is a complex process that involves evaluating many elements within the supply chain. A first step in this analysis is the application of various tools that allow the identification of risks to achieve an assessment (Soler Anguiano and Álvarez Echeverría, 2010). In this way, each of the actors can take action and have an acceptable balance of disruptive factors or events and costs.

Because it is not possible to have control of all sources of risk, various authors such as Sheffi (2005) and Ardilla (2014) propose that rather than determining risk

factors, special attention should be paid to the failure modes of the system before involvement by a disruptive event. Ardilla (2014), categorizes the failure modes as follows in table 1:

Table 1: Failure Mode Categories

Failure mode	
Supply failure	Any interruption of supply-related activities, such as shortages, delay or availability
Demand failure	Permanent or temporary delay of the claim that leads to its loss
Transport failure	Delays or failures in transportation infrastructure leading to inability to transport goods or services
Facility failure	Failures in the infrastructure of offices, buildings or warehouses that prevent the performance of operations
Communication network failure	Failures in the communications infrastructure inside or outside the company that prevents the coordination of operations
Commercial cargo violations	Refers to the violation of the integrity of the cargo that leads to the loss or adulteration of property

The disruptions to which a supply chain is subject include natural events, problems in supply and/or demand, changes in human organizational behavior, technological, financial or legal problems.

Natural events bring with them many social effects that have significant impacts on industries by altering the global supply chain (Khojasteh, 2018). To mitigate the impacts before these types of events, companies propose strategies that strengthen their production and distribution mechanisms.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

The location of facilities is a decisive element in the strategic planning of any system or supply chain, whose structure determines the efficiency of its activities to satisfy demand. Location problems arise from the need to locate a product, service or installation in the best possible way. Sibert (2011) defines location problems in a general way as a set of clients distributed in a geographical area and whose demand for product or service must be met by one or more facilities.

In addition, the decision process for the location of the facilities in the desired territory must take into account the client's requirements and needs, as well as geographic restrictions. These decisions allow determining the allocation of customers, as well as the capacity of the facilities.

Currently, there are various mathematical models that are used to address facility location problems according to specific cases (objectives, variables and restrictions). Some examples of these models are: weighted factors, location-allocation, coverage / anti-

coverage, center of gravity, shortest route, transportation, among others.

One of the most widely used mathematical models in locating facilities is the maximum coverage model that is focused on maximizing coverage given a predefined number of facilities. The formulation of the coverage model considers a discrete set of demand points, which are assigned to assign a weight according to the conditions of the problem, and a discrete set of candidate locations in which it is decided to open or not a facility (González-Solano, 2015).

In his research work González-Solano (2015) proposes to design robust supply chains, capable of withstanding adversities caused by events such as: hurricanes, tornadoes, earthquakes, labor protests, accidents, among others. Through nonlinear integer programming models to determine the optimal location of facilities under cost and reliability criteria.

Amaya (2017) proposes to determine the best location for several priority health care centers, using maximum coverage location models and genetic algorithms in such a way that it is possible to decrease the average distance and increase the number of inhabitants covered, taking into account the pre-existing facilities. The same approach was also proposed by Baeza (2015) who focuses on the optimal distribution of health services through the maximum coverage location model.

Montufar's (2019) research, presents a proposal for the relocation of distribution centers using a coverage optimization model in order to find the fewest number of facilities that allow reducing the distances that residents travel to buy groceries.

To address the different location problems Carro ("s.f") proposes a classification structure:

- Location of a single installation. This type of problem only considers the location of a facility without interaction with others, its main decision criteria are: labor costs, supply, demand, labor available in the area, services, taxes, etc.
- Location of multiple factories and warehouses. Other existing facilities are considered in this type of problem and the main decision criterion is cost reduction.
- Location of competitive retail stores. This type of problem contemplates the selection of points for shops of any branch or activity and its main decision criteria are the relative distance between points of sale, competition and the distance that consumers must travel.
- Location of emergency services. This type of problem includes fire stations, police, hospitals, supplies, etc. Its main decision criterion is the speed of response to any emergency.

4. BACKGROUND

4.1. Background of the Iztapalapa city hall

The Iztapalapa city hall is made up of 293 colonies, in which 1,827,345 citizens live (Programa provisional de

gobierno, 2020). Iztapalapa is the most populated demarcation in Mexico and its population density represents one of the highest burdens in terms of the probability of infection (Barrios, 2020).

According to Mayor Clara Brugada, more than 700 thousand poor people live in the district, in addition to the fact that 60 thousand families do not have direct access to drinking water in their homes. The National Council for the Evaluation of Social Development Policy (CONEVAL) (2019), through the study Measurement of Poverty in Mexico 2015, announced that of the total population living in Iztapalapa, 35% live in poverty and 1.7% in extreme poverty. In addition, the same source reported that approximately 234 thousand 535 people, more than 12% of the mayor's population, lack access to food.

This reality imposes a dynamic on the population of Iztapalapa in which informal employment or self-employment is the only source of economic income for its inhabitants (ALDF, 2013). According to the CDMX Government Headquarters, in the Iztapalapa city hall there are more than 300 tianguis that settle each week in different neighborhoods of the demarcation, which is an example of the enormous weight that the informal economy has in this CDMX region.

On the other hand, Aurora Melo, leader of the Federation of Mexican Unions A.C. He highlighted that in Iztapalapa there are 90 thousand registered tianguistas (plus thousands more without registration) (Olson, 2020). César Hernández, president of the National Coordinator of Merchants and Popular Organizations, affirmed that around 50 percent of the register sells a basic basket, that is, 45 thousand merchants (Olson, 2020). In addition, it is worth mentioning that in this demarcation the CDMX Supply Center is located, which covers a large part of the regional and even national demand for food and is considered one of the largest in Latin America (Iztapalapa Mexico City, 2016).

4.2. H1N1 background in Iztapalapa city hall

H1N1 influenza is a viral infection that attacks the respiratory airways, including the lung. H1N1 is transmitted from person to person by speaking or sneezing and can be confused with severe flu-like illness (Ponce, 2009). On April 24, 2009, due to the rapid spread of H1N1 influenza in Mexico, it was necessary to apply sanitary measures such as the use of mouth masks and gel alcohol in public places, the closure of schools nationwide, suspension of activities non-essential and social distancing (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2009).

The results of the study carried out by Zepeda-Lopez (2009) showed that the highest number of cases of influenza A (H1N1) in 2009 were observed in the most populated areas of Mexico City, in particular the neighborhoods on the northeast side, including Iztapalapa, Gustavo A. Madero, Iztacalco and Tláhuac (figure 1). In addition, the results allowed accepting the hypothesis that the high population density and a massive meeting that took place in Iztapalapa during holy week

contributed to the rapid spread of the disease that developed in three peaks of activity throughout the country (figure 2).

Figure 1: Municipalities with the highest number of infected people. Source: Zepeda-Lopez (2009)

Figure 2: H1N1 spikes across the country. Source: Zepeda-Lopez (2009)

5. SOLUTIONS

5.1. CDMX government solution

Claudia Sheinbaum, head of government of the CDMX, pointed out that her government's solution regarding “tianguis” to mitigate contagions, was to grant loans of 25.00 pesos to informal merchants to support the epidemic by COVID-19. These credits were granted with 0% interest and four months to pay. In total, around 2,500 million pesos contributed by the federal government were allocated (Navarrete, 2020). For her part, Clara Brugada, mayor of Iztapalapa, assured that during May more than 2.17 million people stopped concentrating due to the closure of the street markets (press release, 2020). This solution does not fully attend to the needs of the population since, on the one hand, the credit granted to the “tianguistas” only covers those registered, leaving aside those who are not. In addition, the scenario of the health emergency extending for a longer period and reducing the food supply is not contemplated, causing slight crowds in “recauderías” and popular markets near the colonies.

5.2. Alternative proposal

Due to the sanitary emergency, it was proposed to determine different individual locations so that the fruit and vegetable stands guarantee the supply of these essential items to the families of the Iztapalapa city hall, taking population density and the degree of contagion as the main factors in the different sectors and colonies of the demarcation. In this way, the distribution channel of essential goods is given a certain flexibility, allowing it to respond to the economic needs of merchants and to attend to health recommendations by minimizing the agglomeration of buyers and neighboring street stands.

The location of the different locations of the street markets is carried out using a maximum coverage location model.

6. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used for this work is as follows:

- Description of the problem
- Selection of the colonies of the Iztapalapa city hall
- Formulation of the mathematical model
- Results

6.1. Description of the problem

The recommendations issued by the health authorities to mitigate the transmission by COVID-19 for the purchase of merchandise, stipulate that the “healthy distance” (1.5 m) must be maintained when ordering, receiving and paying, the permanent use of mouthguards and avoiding the physical contact (Ministry of health, 2020). However, Clara Brugada, mayor of the district, recognizes that reducing mobility, as well as complying with these recommendations, is a very complex task because Iztapalapa faces problems such as high population and high poverty. Due to the aforementioned, the government launched an operation to cordon off the street markets in the area, so that there were only two accesses and exits for consumers and only one adult per family was allowed to pass, after washing hands, gel application, and mouthpiece placement (press release, 2020).

Despite the recommendations and efforts of the authorities, the low vigilance in compliance with the regulations, the structures with little space presented by street vendors (figure 3), as well as the omission of sanitary recommendations by vendors and customers that attend the tianguis; they favor that the zones are places of contagion.

Figure 3: Conventional distribution of a tianguis. Source: By authors

Undoubtedly, the problem to be faced is due to the high contagion rate derived from the reproductive number (R_0) presented by COVID-19 in Mexico, which describes the speed of spread among the population, a comparative with respect to other respiratory diseases such as Seasonal influenza and H1N1 are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Reproductive number R_0 of respiratory diseases in Mexico. Source: Public Health

6.2. Selection of the colonies of the Iztapalapa city hall

The Iztapalapa mayor's office has a total of 293 colonies, of which two have a recidivism on July 26, 2020 at a red light, indicating a high number of COVID-19 infections in a given period, these colonies are: Año de Juárez and Barrio de Guadalupe. Due to population density and the degree of marginalization (SIDESO, 2020) Barrio de Guadalupe was selected for the analysis, its geographical location was obtained from Google Maps (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Barrio de Guadalupe

6.3. Mathematical model formulation

In this case, the coverage model is applied in order to achieve a distribution such that the stands of tianguis have enough distance to avoid crowds and satisfy the "healthy distance" recommendations between customers and vendors. At the same time, it helps to reduce the mobility of people by reducing the distance they must travel to make their purchases.

In the case of the neighborhood of Barrio de Guadalupe, it was proposed to place nodes in each corner of the streets and outlying circumferences that grouped between seven and nine nodes so that the inhabitants of the area travel minimum distances to each location. In this way, a total of four coverage circumferences with a total of 29 nodes were determined.

The decision variable was determined with respect to placing the stands or not in a certain location as seen below:

$$x_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{se instala el puesto} \\ 0, & \text{otro caso} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Whose objective function remains as the minimum of positions to be placed achieving the desired coverage:

$$\text{Min} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} C_i X_i \quad (2)$$

Where, C_i is a cost associated with the node.

In this case, as it only seeks to locate sales points, it was used with a value equal to one. However, the construction of the constraints obeys the coverage circumferences proposed.

The solution of the coverage model approach was obtained with the help of the Lingo 18.0 software, which was used to obtain an optimal solution to the problem caused by the installation of stations and subject to the proposed coverage radii (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Lingo Solution

6.4. Results

The results obtained indicate that with a total of nine points of sale that could meet the food purchase needs of the residents of the neighborhood of Barrio de Guadalupe, these being nodes 2, 4, 8, 11, 14, 17, 19, 22, 25 and 27 respectively, as shown in figure 7.

Figure 8: Proposed points of sale

In this way, the positions obtained by the coverage model have a location such that users have a nearby location that allows them to follow the recommendations of the authorities in the face of the COVID-19 health emergency. At this point it is recommended that the vendors assigned to each neighborhood should be close to their places of residence to reduce transportation costs.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Through models such as coverage, it was possible to arrive at a distribution of locations that allows clients to access each post on each of the streets that are part of the neighborhood. Through this solution, it is possible to maintain the economic activity of people dedicated to the sale of goods in street markets without generating large crowds of people, which implies adapting to respond to changes according to the propagation conditions of COVID-19.

As future work, it remains to explore the viability of the new locations for the stalls through simulation

techniques, as well as the implementation of more robust models that allow considering the volume of food consumption per person in the coverage area to dimension from properly size the stands.

REFERENCES

- ALDF, (2014). Partido verde ecologista de México. Retrieved from: <http://www.aldf.gob.mx/archivo-5920e38ef3d7cc9f9ea1a4b1e0b121f8.pdf>
- Amaya G. Ciro A., Hernández H. Juan S., Sampayo O. Ernesto F. (2017). Problema de máxima cobertura aplicado a centros de atención atención en la salud: aproximación mediante algoritmos genéticos.
- Ardila Weimar A., Romero Daniel H, González Fernando R. (2014). Estrategias para la Gestión de Riesgos en la Cadena de Suministros. Universidad Autónoma del Caribe, Barranquilla, Colombia. 12th Latin American and Caribbean Conference for Engineering and Technology Guayaquil, Ecuador July 22-24, 2014
- Baeza Sanz Manuel, (2015). Localización de servicios: modelos de cubrimiento. Departamento de estadística i investigación operativa. Valladolid.
- Carro Paz Roberto, González Gómez Daniel, (“s.f”). Localización de las instalaciones. Facultad de ciencias económicas y sociales. Universidad nacional del mar de plata. Vol 13.
- Bojórquez López Claudia Guadalupe, Guaderrama Aurora Máynez, (2016). La resiliencia en la cadena de suministros: un análisis a través del mapa de flujo de valor, revisión de literatura. Universidad Autónoma de ciudad Juárez.
- Barrios Luis E. (2020). Coronavirus: la larga pesadilla en Iztapalapa. Retrieved from: <https://marxismo.mx/coronavirus-la-larga-pesadilla-en-iztapalapa/>
- Bukowski, L, Feliks, J. (2012). Multi-dimensional concept of supply chain resilience. Paper presented at the CLC 2012: Carpathian Logistics Congress
- Calvenet, A. (2007). Resiliencia: un concepto clave para la sustentabilidad. En UAIS (4). Argentina: Complejidad y sustentabilidad.
- Carro Paz, R., & González Gómez, D. (2012). Localización de instalaciones. Administración de las Operaciones, 25.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Outbreak of swine-origin influenza A (H1N1) virus infection — Mexico, March– April 2009.
- Chávez Orduña, M. (2010). Estudio de localización para una empresa fabricante de herramientas. México: UNAM.
- Comunicado de prensa, (2020). Retrieved from: <http://www.iztapalapa.cdmx.gob.mx/boletines/?bo1=1219>
- Conoce México. (21 de marzo de 2019). México Desconocido. Obtenido de <https://www.mexicodesconocido.com.mx/tianguis-mercado-prehispanico.html>
- Cotte Urrutia Ana María (2018). Cadenas de suministro resilientes. Trabajo Final del programa de

- especialización en gerencia logística integral. Universidad militar nueva granada, facultad de ingeniería.
- Gaceta oficial de la ciudad de México (2019). Retrieved from: http://www.sideso.cdmx.gob.mx/documentos/2019/alcaldias/iztapalapa/116iztapalapa_reducirlaextremadepobrezaenlaalcaldia.pdf
- Gil, A. J. (2018). Localización de almacenes como problema de diversidad máxima para aumentar la resiliencia en la cadena de suministro en México. México: UNAM.
- Iztapalapa Ciudad de México, México (2016). Informe final de la demarcación. Retrieved from: <https://infonavit.janium.net/janium/Documentos/58000.pdf>
- Jefatura de gobierno CDMX (2020). Entrevista a la Jefa de Gobierno. Retrieved from: <https://www.jefaturadegobierno.cdmx.gob.mx/>
- Navarrete Shelma (2020). Tianguistas de la CDMX recibirán créditos por 25,000 pesos. Expansión política. Retrieved from: <https://politica.expansion.mx/cdmx/2020/05/19/tianguistas-de-la-cdmx-recibiran-creditos-por-25-000-pesos>.
- Montufar-Benítez, Marco A., Montañón-Arango Oscar, Corona-Armenta, José R, Rivera-Gómez, Héctor. (2019). Aplicación del Modelo de Cobertura de Conjuntos a la Localización de Centros de Distribución de Mercancías dentro de la Ciudad de Pachuca, Hidalgo. Boletín científico del instituto de ciencias básicas e ingeniería.
- Murino Teresa, Romano Elpidio, Santillo Liberatina C. (2011). Modelling Supply Chain Resilience. *Department of Materials Engineering and Operations Management, University of Naples “Federico II”, Piazzale.
- Murino Teresa, Romano Elpidio, Santillo Liberatina C. (2011). Supply chain performance sustainability through resilience function. Proceedings of the 2011 Winter Simulation Conference. University of Naples “Federico II”.
- Mundy, B. (2014). La fuente del tianguis de San Juan de México-Tenochtitlan y el segundo acueducto de Chapultepec. Boletín de Monumentos Históricos, 9-25.
- Olson Georgina, Roa Wendy (2020). Imposible que tianguistas de Iztapalapa regresen el lunes: Clara Brugada. Excelsior. Retrieved from: <https://www.excelsior.com.mx/comunidad/imposible-que-tianguistas-de-iztapalapa-regresen-el-lunes-clara-brugada/1384937>.
- Olson Georgina (2020). Tianguistas vuelven el próximo lunes; iniciarán con 31 mil 500 en Iztapalapa. Excelsior. Retrieved from: <https://www.excelsior.com.mx/comunidad/tianguistas-vuelven-el-proximo-lunes-iniciaran-con-31-mil-500-en-iztapalapa/1384685>.
- Ponce López María Luisa (2009). La Influenza A H1N1 en México Diagnóstico, tratamiento y prevención. Vertientes. Revista especializada de la salud. Vol 12, No 1-2. UNAM.
- Programa provisional de gobierno (2020). Retrieved from: <http://www.iztapalapa.cdmx.gob.mx/concejales/pdf/ProgPro19-20.pdf>
- Resilience Alliance (2020). Key concepts / Resilience. Retrieved from: <https://www.resalliance.org/resilience>.
- Salud pública, (2020). Retrieved from: <https://www.smsp.org.mx/covid-19-prevencion-poblacion.html>
- Secretaria de salud (2020), Sana distancia COVID-19. Retrieved from: <https://www.gob.mx/salud/documentos/sana-distancia>.
- Sheffi, Y. (2005). The Resilient Enterprise. Overcoming Vulnerability for Competitive Advantage. Effects of Disruptions.
- Siebert Pinedo Karyn, Quintana Pinedo Christian José, (2011). Determinación de puntos óptimos para la localización e implantación de plantas de biodiésel en el estado de Tocantins Determination of optimal points to the location and establishment of biodiésel plants in the state of Tocantins. Revista Electrónica Nova Scientia, N° 7 Vol. 4 (1), 2011. ISSN 2007 - 0705. pp: 35 – 54.
- SIDESO. Sistema de Información del Desarrollo Social. Delegación Iztapalpa. Retrieved from: <http://www.sideso.cdmx.gob.mx/index.php?id=63>
- Soler Anguiano, F., & Alvarez Echeverria, F. (2010). ¿Por qué hacer estudios de riesgo? México: Facultad de Ingeniería, UNAM.
- Supply chain resilience guide (2019), Home land security. Retrieved from: <https://www.fema.gov/media-library-data/1555328671083-d9422177bd55d9c6fafc327a6b239290/SupplyChainResilienceGuide-April2019.pdf>
- Wicher Pavel, Radim Lenort (2012). The ways of creating resilient supply chains. Škoda auto University, VŠB – Technical University of Ostrava
- Zepeda-Lopez Hector M., Perea-Araujo Lizbeth, Miliar-García Angel, Dominguez-López Aarón, Xoconostle-Cázarez Beatriz, Lara-Padilla Eleazar, Ramírez Hernández Jorge A., Sevilla-Reyes Edgar, Orozco Maria Esther, Ahued-Ortega Armando, Villaseñor-Ruiz Ignacio, Garcia-Cavazos Ricardo J., Teran Luis M. (2009). Inside the Outbreak of the 2009 Influenza A (H1N1)v Virus in Mexico. PLoS ONE, vol 5, issue 10.
- Khojasteh, Y. (2018). Supply Chain Risk Management. Tokio, Japón: Springer.
- Zsidisin, G., & Ritchie, B. (2009). Supply Chain Risk. USA: Springer.